

CESSDA

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

Annual Report 2016

www.cessda.eu

Preface

Over the past 2 years, significant developments took place in CESSDA. From being established as a permanent legal entity in 2013, CESSDA has undergone significant changes, both in size of its internal operations, and its external activities in European arena. While internal developments were connected mostly to further building of its technical infrastructure and training activities, CESSDA invested substantial efforts in “external” engagement through participation in more EU funded projects, in cooperation with a number of organisations, and in initiatives of interest for the social sciences and academic community in general.

Strengthening relationships with other social sciences and humanities research infrastructures, with the entire ERIC Network, as well as with the extended network of potential member countries and service providers, gave CESSDA more visibility and has started the process of positioning CESSDA as the major stakeholder on European level.

All the activities carried out in CESSDA are a result of hard work of people from 15 European member countries, their service providers and the staff at the main office in Bergen. Their expertise, commitment and enthusiasm were the driving forces in the last year. At strategic level, there were a number of meetings with the Scientific Advisory Board and with the Board of Directors. And the hard work paid off – in European and CESSDA Projects, during expertise seminars for members, at conferences, and at meetings with new members. ERIC status is expected to be received from the EC in 2017.

CESSDA is now ready for the next phase of its development. In November 2016, Ron Dekker was appointed as the new Director of CESSDA. He will assume his duties in early 2017. We are ready to lead CESSDA into the new phase over the next years.

Sincerely,

Ivana Ilijasic Versic, Acting Administrative Director

and

Ron Dekker, Director – as of March 2017

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About CESSDA

The mission of CESSDA is to provide a full scale sustainable research infrastructure that enables the research community to conduct high-quality research which in turn leads to effective solutions to the major challenges facing society today. To achieve it, CESSDA supports national and international research and cooperation in the social, economic and political sciences and in areas that correspond to long-term European strategic documents such as Europe 2020.

CESSDA stands for the provision of cross-European resource discovery and for improved quality of data and metadata. It strives to offer a wider selection of comparable data. Certification of data archiving organisations is mandatory and is one of several obligations which apply to data services which are part of CESSDA. CESSDA provides professional training modules for data archivists and the scientific community across Europe. And finally, it strongly advocates involvement and cooperation with organisations outside Europe and on the global scale.

The technical and scientific description (TSD) of CESSDA states that social science researchers across the European Research Area (ERA) should be supported by providing a comprehensive and integrated social science data research infrastructure that facilitates and supports

research, teaching and learning of the highest quality throughout the social sciences and beyond. It is achieved through the development and coordination of standards, protocols and professional best practices pertaining to the access to and curation of data and associated digital objects, and by facilitating researchers' access to relevant resources of the European social sciences' research agenda.

CESSDA's objectives ensure seamless access to data across repositories, nations, languages and research purposes, encourage standardisation of data and metadata, data enrichment, data sharing and knowledge mobility across Europe, thus stimulating increased scientific use of high quality, publicly-funded data.

About CESSDA

CESSDA's main objectives are:

- » To support national and international research and cooperation in the social sciences by providing a research infrastructure for data ingest, curation, and access (including discoverability) services;
- » To facilitate and promote more and wider use of high-quality data in social, economic and political research and, in turn, improve our understanding of ongoing societal processes, the problems involved and the solutions available;
- » To provide a comprehensive, distributed and integrated social science data research infrastructure that will facilitate and support research, teaching and learning of the highest quality throughout the social sciences in the European Research Area
- » To develop and coordinate standards, protocols and professional best practice;
- » To facilitate access to social science data resources for researchers regardless of the location of either researcher or data within the European Research Area, and beyond;
- » To enable, extend and promote access agreements, licensing models, and any other legal and organisational measure that enables and extends such access to distributed data resources, while taking account of the specific national requirements;
- » To actively contribute to the development, promotion and adoption of standards for data distribution and data management, thereby enhancing the quality of infrastructural services;
- » To work continuously to include further data sources, from Europe and beyond, into the infrastructure;
- » To provide training within CESSDA and beyond on best practices surrounding operational processes and data management;
- » To promote and facilitate wider participation in CESSDA.

International Cooperation

CESSDA's members can be found across the whole of Europe and therefore all of its activities are de facto international. However, CESSDA is also involved in a number of joint projects with external international partners.

Work Plan Tasks

CESSDA operates on the basis of yearly work plans, which are made up of a number of tasks. Each task is led by one Service Provider (SP) and involves a number of other Service Providers. Engagement is based on expertise, capacity and availability. The following Work Plans have been adopted since 2014: WP2015, WP2016, and in November 2016, CESSDA General Assembly adopted the next Work Plan for 2017.

The majority of tasks in 2016 were connected to technical developments in CESSDA. The Work Plan 2016 was adopted by the CESSDA General Assembly in February 2016 and builds on the previous Work Plan (WP2015). For this reason, it began mid 2016, upon finalisation of most tasks from WP2015. The following tasks were launched in June 2016:

CESSDA Product and Service Catalogue – Phase 1

The CESSDA Product and Service Catalogue project is proposed to run in four implementation phases during the next three years. The Products and Services catalogue is intended to provide a one-stop-shop for search/discovery of data sets relevant to social science research, by harvesting the metadata describing SP's holdings and making it browsable and searchable. Each phase will add additional functionality, so that the utility and ease of use of the product grows with each release.

It must be compliant with other CESSDA projects, such as the CESSDA Metadata Model (CMM), the Euro Question Bank, or the Open Source Metadata Harvester from 2015.

In 2016, the project gathered and refined the user requirements, and developed a demonstrator/pilot version. The project plan for Phase 2 was also developed.

Participants: UKDS (lead), CESSDA MO¹, FSD, GESIS, NSD, SND.

¹ CESSDA Main Office

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CESSDA Technical Framework - Phase 2

The CESSDA Technical framework project provided a development environment that would speed up the process for developing service components (such as the Product and Service Catalogue) without the need for Service Providers to install, configure and maintain a suite of software development tools within their own infrastructure.

Subsequent phases of the Technical Framework project will provide a deployment environment that the live service components will run in, as well as maintaining existing service components and integrating new ones.

Participants: UKDS (lead), CESSDA MO, DANS, FSD, FORS, GESIS, NSD.

Training modules for “Data Discovery”

The Training task was delivered by the CESSDA Training Group and proposed the development of a new area of expertise: [Data Discovery](#).

The project aimed to improve user experience by making it easier for users to identify the correct data for their needs. Based on the lead partner expertise (UK Data Service), this allowed CESSDA users to locate and navigate data collections of the various service providers.

The modules described were delivered over the period running from June 2016 to 30 June 2017. Activities undertaken during the course of this task included assessment of end user training needs and existing training capacity across the CESSDA Service Providers.

A landscape mapping exercise took place to give insight into the data landscape experienced by researchers. Lastly, two types of training content were designed and delivered during the project period: three webinars and a video.

Webinars covered several topics of interest to the scientific community and archiving professionals. The benefits will be extended further when this information is added to the

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Knowledge Sharing Platform (KSP) built in the framework of the EU-funded CESSDA SaW project.

Participants: GESIS and UKDS (lead), all Service Providers.

Euro Question Bank - Phase 2

The aim of the Euro Question Bank (EQB) project was to develop and implement a central search facility across all CESSDA's survey questions of different data sets in different languages, and also to cover as many questions of surveys as possible. EQB allows exploring particular topics to identify existing survey items.

This makes it possible for researchers in any country to identify questions that pertain to their research interests for the purposes of discovery or survey creation. Upon its completion, the Euro Question Bank will be linked to or integrated into other CESSDA systems, including the CESSDA Data Portal, the ELSST Thesaurus, CESSDA survey design and management tool, and the CharmStats harmonization software.

The project started initially in July 2015 (phase 1) with basic infrastructure plan and preliminary implementation. The design of user interfaces and testing with content and revised implementation took place in 2016, while broad application of the concept is planned together with enhanced functionality across CESSDA Service Providers in 2017.

Participants: GESIS (lead), FORS, FSD, NSD, SND, UKDS.

Develop and establish the CESSDA PID Policy for the data registration and service/persistent identifiers within CESSDA

The persistent identification (PID) of data sets has been on the agenda for several years. The ability to easily locate and access digital resources and then associate them with the related metadata is essential to allow for the citation, retrieval and preservation of those data.

Therefore, for research infrastructures such as CESSDA, there has to be a clear policy with respect to persistent and unique identifiers which provide value to researchers, and are practical to implement across the CESSDA SP without significantly altering local practices.

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The CESSDA Persistent Identifier Policy was intended to support the aims of locating, discovering, referencing, identifying and citing CESSDA SP data holdings. It serves as a basis for a common approach to the use of PID services across the CESSDA SP.

The policy contains requirements regarding the use of PID to which the CESSDA SP must adhere. The principles of the PID Policy are aligned with the CESSDA Statutes and the CESSDA Data Access Policy.

The PID Policy framework covers the general principles for the use of Persistent Identifiers across CESSDA SP and contains Best Practice Guidelines.

Participants: GESIS (lead), DANS, SND.

CESSDA Expert Seminar 2016

The CESSDA Expert Seminar 2016 ([CES2016](#)) was presented by the CESSDA Technical Working Group and hosted by the Czech Social Science Data Archive (CSDA) in Prague on 13 and 14 September 2016.

The focus of the seminar was on developing components for the CESSDA Research Infrastructure and it was aimed at technical managers and software developers. This was a closed event for European Data Archives that are CESSDA Service Providers, observers and aspiring Service Providers. There were twenty five participants.

One of the key objectives of the CESSDA Technical Roadmap is to ensure that CESSDA has access to its software assets and also develops and retains the capability to maintain, enhance, quality assure and run them. To this end, the programme of CES2016 was a combination of theoretical and hands-on sessions, giving both a broad introduction to how CESSDA will manage the production of software components for its Research Infrastructure, and an in-depth look at some of the tools that have been adopted to support the development of components.

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Micro-service architectures, cloud computing, software maturity modelling and Continuous Delivery were amongst the topics discussed, as these are important enablers for achieving the technical vision.

Trust activities 2016

Trust activities have been ongoing within the CESSDA community since 2013. It was revitalised with the submission and then beginning of the EU funded CESSDA SaW project.

The main objective of this task was to ensure that all the Data Seal of Approval obligations (now DSA/WDS requirements) are met by all Service Providers, as well as aligning DSA Guidelines with CESSDA Obligations for Service Providers (as stated in the Annex 2 of the CESSDA Statutes).

Trust activities would be extended beyond the duration of the CESSDA SAW project and are coordinated by the Trust Support Working Group, established in 2015.

In the course of 2016, this task evaluated already existing ideas and plans concerning trust issues within CESSDA.

Three categories of Service Providers were established: already certified, close to certification, and starters.

The period from June 2016 until the end of the year was a testing period for the assessment procedure; every Service Provider which had not yet obtained the DSA, was invited to use this period for testing the DSA/WDS assessment criteria and procedure.

Participants: DANS (lead), all Service Providers and extended CESSDA SaW network.

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CESSDA Technical Roadmap

The first version of the CESSDA Technical Roadmap was completed in December 2016 by the CESSDA Technical Working Group. It is aimed at potential suppliers of software items (applications, components, utilities etc.) for use within the CESSDA Research Infrastructure - in the first instance this will be the CESSDA Service Providers, but could potentially be any software development organisation.

"We have laid firm foundations and set clear guidelines for the future growth of CESSDA's technical infrastructure."

- John Shepherdson
Associate Director, Technical Services, UK Data Service

The intention is to ensure that the direction of travel with respect to building and maintaining CESSDA's technical Research Infrastructure is clear to all concerned.

The document provides a high-level view of CESSDA's technical development work, so that readers can get a sense of what is in place, and what is to come on a year by year basis. It includes work plan activities, Annex 6 activities described in the CESSDA Statutes, and relevant work package tasks of EU-funded projects (such as CESSDA SaW and SERISS). Some of the items are highly speculative at this stage, and little detail (such as task description and timescales) is available. They are included as placeholders for completeness, and will be expanded or removed in subsequent revisions, as appropriate.

European Union Funded Projects

CESSDA MO and its data service providers take part in a number of international projects of relevance to its mission. CESSDA AS is a grant beneficiary in three Horizon 2020 projects as follows:

Big Data Europe - Empowering Communities with Data Technologies

The Big Data Europe (BDE) project started in 2015 and is due to run for 36 months.

CESSDA's role is to coordinate the input of the stakeholders of the Societal Challenge 6: Europe in a changing world - Inclusive, reflective and innovative society, in order to assist building a requirements specification for a new Big Data Aggregator platform. Once built, the aggregator will be used by CESSDA members and other research infrastructures in order to explore the value of big data, to evaluate the benefits of these new data sources to the social sciences and humanities, and to learn about the implications of managing and

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preserving these sources of data from the perspective of an archive.

In 2016, BDE was successfully reviewed by the European Commission and independent evaluators, as it was half way through its lifetime. CESSDA co-hosted a workshop in Cologne on 5 December 2016 on “The Challenges of Big Data for societies in a changing world”, along with three webinars in the course of the year: “New General Data Protection Regulation Adopted” (25 May), “European Open Science Agenda: Quo Vadis?” (30 May), and “Citizens’ budget at municipal level” (28 September).

CESSDA SaW - Strengthening and Widening

CESSDA Main Office is the coordinator of the CESSDA SaW project. This is a 2-year project with the primary ambition of establishing the conditions for a seamless social science data archive service for the whole of the European Research Area (ERA), capable of supporting the research needs of the next generation of social scientists wherever they may be.

As project coordinator, CESSDA is heavily involved in all aspects of the project. Tasks

carried out in 2016 range from the establishment of a knowledge sharing platform for ERA data archives and a hub, delivering a state of play evaluation of social science data archives and services in European Economic Area countries, identifying gaps and bottlenecks in existing services and producing national development plans to close the gaps and overcome present barriers.

In the course of the year the first or four planned workshops was held in the Netherlands. It was devoted to

trust activities. The second consortium meeting was held in Bergen, and the third one in Budapest, Hungary, which facilitated hungarian efforts towards membership in CESSDA. In July 2016, CESSDA SAW completed its first year and was successfully reviewed by the European Commission and an independent reviewer.

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SERISS - “Synergies for Europe’s Research Infrastructures in the Social Sciences”

SERISS is a 4-year project which brings together three research infrastructures in the social sciences: the European Social Survey (ESS), the Survey for Health Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) and the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA), along with some aspiring infrastructures.

The project started in 2015 and CESSDA participates via five of its Service Providers as well as staff at the Main Office.

SERISS focuses on three broad themes: addressing key challenges for cross-national data collection, breaking down barriers between infrastructures and embracing the future of social sciences.

In 2016, the main issue was alignment of technical developments in the course of the SERISS project, and CESSDA technical standards. That was needed in order to accommodate interactive tools for cross-national surveys on the CESSDA website. Significant advancements were made in the area of legal and ethical challenges facing cross-national social science research.

New Proposals in 2016

The following project proposals were submitted to the European Commission in 2016:

DwB2 - Data without Boundaries 2

The project would provide the overall framework and infrastructure necessary for dramatically enhancing the use of official and administrative microdata by researchers,

“Since July 2015 CESSDA ERIC has been a key partner in the Horizon2020 project Synergies for Europe’s Research Infrastructures in the Social Sciences (SERISS), coordinated by European Social Survey (ESS) ERIC. Data protection experts at CESSDA (NSD) are leading a workpackage to explore the legal and ethical issues around new forms of social science data and have been providing invaluable help to Europe’s survey infrastructures as they prepare for the introduction of the General Data Protection Regulation in 2018. CESSDA colleagues at FORS, GESIS and NSD are working closely with researchers from ESS and the European Values Study on a suite of online tools that will improve our ability to manage the survey lifecycle efficiently and to document survey metadata effectively. This ongoing collaboration between CESSDA and other leading social science research infrastructures in Europe serves to strengthen and harmonise social science research, equipping the infrastructures to meet future challenges and ensuring that national and European policymakers can continue to draw on socio-economic evidence of the highest quality.”

- Professor Rory Fitzgerald
ESS ERIC Director
and SERISS Coordinator

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particularly confidential and sensitive data across borders.

This represents a core objective for the communities involved in the preparation of the project proposal: data producers/data owners, data accreditors, data providers and data users.

The project would build on the [Data without boundaries project](#) which ended in April 2015. The project would aim to accomplish the following: foster discussions at a high level on the legal frameworks that impact access to data, cooperate with the Research Data Centres providing access to confidential data, set up a Distributed Secure Research System for Research Data Centres together with a metadata system for discovery and use of such data. Having CESSDA as a partner would help ensure the sustainability of the project outputs, not least thanks to the cooperation with various stakeholders at national and European level relevant to access to official and administrative data.

PopLife - An Integrated Community On Population and Life Course Dynamics

PopLife aims to link population data, researchers and stakeholders into an Integrated Population Research Community. This would allow for better use of existing resources, more coordination among international and national survey infrastructures, as well as easier access to additional types of data. PopLife proposes to integrate data from social media, population registries and web analytics into survey infrastructures and thus tried to dramatically increase the scientific power of such infrastructures.

Cutting edge research on the causes and consequences of demographic changes would thus be conducted. The overarching aim of PopLife is therefore to provide researchers and stakeholders with an integrated community with access to the best and most innovative resources to study the causes and consequences of population change.

Trust4Data - Core Certification for Data Repositories in an Open Science Infrastructure

The objective of this proposal is to establish a Core Certification Service for research data repositories. The project would build on the work carried out within the Research Data Alliance, to integrate the current fragmented first attempts for (self-)certification into a system of Core Certification, that can be deployed by any and all data repositories willing to join the European Open Science Cloud. It would develop and create a standard information

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(object and process) model for Core Certification, which would be deployed within a dedicated group of early adopters.

Trust4Data would bring together the key players in the field: leading members of ICSU/WDS (World Data System) and DSA (Data Seal of Approval) who have successfully established the first certification practices within their own multidisciplinary, global communities. The idea is to integrate these models into one new Core Certification Service, which would make it accessible to a wider group of data repositories, first and foremost those aiming to play a role in the European Open Science Cloud.

RISCAPE - European Research Infrastructures in the International Landscape

The proposal aims at providing a peer-reviewed international landscape analysis report on the position and complementarities of the major European research infrastructures in the international research infrastructure landscape. Such a report would be systematic, focused, of high quality, comprehensive and consistent. The resulting report and the used methods should contribute to the usability and objectivity of the information provided for the strategic development and policy of European Research Infrastructures. The proposal is directly linked to the European Commission's strategy on EU international cooperation in research and innovation, particularly on the need to obtain objective information in order to help implement it.

Furthermore, CESSDA MO contributed directly to the recent success of the Big Data Europe project, in particular the Societal Challenge 6 "Europe in a Changing World - Inclusive, Innovative and Reflective Societies" activities which are being led by CESSDA MO. Results and efforts in this domain during the past 1.5 years directly influenced (with some other projects and initiatives) the preparation and announcement in October 2015 of the Horizon 2020 call entitled: "[Policy-development in the age of big data: data-driven policy-making, policy-modelling and policy-implementation](#)".

Following this announcement, CESSDA and Fraunhofer IAIS, the coordinator of the BDE project, started work on a project proposal, the deadline for which was February 2017.

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Other Forms of Collaboration

IASSIST

International Association for Social Science Information Services and Technology (IASSIST) is an international organisation working with information technology and data services to support research and teaching in the social sciences. CESSDA has been actively involved in IASSIST activities for many years.

The theme of the 2016 edition of the annual conference was “Embracing the ‘data revolution’: opportunities and challenges for research” and it was the 42nd of its kind, taking place every year.

[IASSIST16](#) took place in Bergen, Norway, from 31 May to 3 June, hosted by NSD - Norwegian Centre for Research Data. CESSDA was presented at several sessions of the IASSIST2016 and the plenary session “CESSDA sets the stage for the data infrastructure of the future” was held on 2 June. This session presented to the audience CESSDA’s activities through engagement on an international level through both external and internal projects.

The three ongoing Horizon 2020 projects in which CESSDA is involved were presented as well as the internal CESSDA project on metadata management led by FSD, the Finnish data archive, from the CESSDA consortium.

Two other presentations of CESSDA’s activities were made during the IASSIST16 conference: “Maturity Model for Assessing Data Infrastructures – CESSDA as an Example”, drawing from the CESSDA SaW project, during the “Data Services: Setting up and evaluating” session on 1 June, and “CESSDA Research Infrastructure – Technical Framework” during the “Technical Data Infrastructure Framework” session on the same day. CESSDA was actively involved in spreading the word about the conference via its website, social media channels and the IASSIST blog.

ICPSR

[ICPSR](#) (Interuniversity Consortium for Political and Social Research) is an international consortium of more than 700 academic institutions and research organisations. ICPSR provides leadership and training in data access, curation, and methods of analysis for the social science research community.

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CESSDA is actively involved in regular ICPSR meetings, and regular communication channels are established with the Main Office which led to joint participation in EU H2020 project CESSDA SaW (Strengthening and Widening). ICPSR will serve as the “industry best” or “gold standard” organisation against which CESSDA will be benchmarked towards the end of the project.

CESSDA has a standing invitation to the ICPSR Council Meetings, and ICPSR representatives regularly attend CESSDA Service Providers’ Forum meetings.

DDI

The [DDI Alliance](#) (Data Documentation Initiative Alliance) is a self-sustaining, multi-institutional membership organisation that develops and promotes the Data Documentation Initiative (DDI) specification and associated tools, education, and outreach programmes.

In July 2016, CESSDA became a member of the DDI Alliance, thus becoming one of a number of organisations from a range of countries, disciplines and sectors committed to developing and maintaining publicly available metadata standards and semantic products for documenting social science and related data.

The DDI Alliance is a programme of the University of Michigan and as the current host institution, and operates within the ICPSR.

RDA

[RDA](#) (Research Data Alliance) is working on building the social and technical bridges to facilitate data sharing and reuse. CESSDA Chief Technical Officer is a member of [GEDE-RDA](#) (Group of European Data Experts-Research Data Alliance), which aims “to promote, foster and drive the discussions and consensus forming on creating guidelines, core components and concrete data fabric configuration building based on a bottom-up process”.

Two virtual meetings took place in 2016, where the goals and charter document were discussed, and one face-to-face meeting was held in November. The meeting was hosted by the Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information (SCSTI) and discussions took place on data challenges, as well as the IRG Roadmap and proposed requirements for an e-infrastructure. A PID focus area was created as a use-case to develop a GEDE approach, where GESIS is the CESSDA representative.

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Eurostat

In 2014, CESSDA considered closer cooperation with [Eurostat](#) and the European Statistics System Committee, in the light of the development of a research strategy for European statistics microdata within the European Statistics System.

CESSDA and possible areas of cooperation were presented to Eurostat in early 2015. The informal cooperation continued in 2016, aiming at the formalisation of joint activities through the Memorandum of Understanding once CESSDA becomes an ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium).

Other forms of cooperation with Eurostat continued in 2016; Eurostat representatives participated in all events organised by CESSDA in the BigDataEurope project and CESSDA was also invited to be a part of the Microdata Access Network Group to be launched in 2017.

CESSDA Communication Activities

The CESSDA website is the primary communication tool for CESSDA with regular inputs from Communication Group members as well as CESSDA Main Office, published monthly and subsequently disseminated via a range of social media platforms (news and events). CESSDA published 30 news items during the course of 2016, sixteen of which were prepared together with members of the group and/or other staff in the Service Providers. An annual review of dissemination activities for CESSDA by group members was gathered in 2016 as well as user data from thirteen archives for the previous year.

In light of CESSDA becoming an ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium), a website review process was launched at the CESSDA Main Office. A policy and media calendar was also kept up to date which showed planned communication activities by CESSDA and its Service Providers throughout the year, based on identified areas of focus for strategic communications. The CESSDA communication strategy should be finalised within CESSDA ERIC, in line with the new CESSDA ERIC Strategic Plan 2018-2022.

A collaboration in terms of communications with the current four ERICs in the social sciences and humanities (CLARIN, DARIAH, ESS, SHARE) was established in 2016 by CESSDA Main Office in order to create synergies and draw on each others' strengths. In addition, the

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PARTHENOS project, which supports the work of CLARIN and DARIAH, as well as CLARIAH, a national counterpart to CLARIN and DARIAH in the Netherlands, were brought on board as an important part of this initiative. Moreover, consultations between CESSDA and the heads

“When archives provide evidence about societies at the individual and the collective level, they tell us stories. A brief one-year-story of SoDaNet_Greece membership in CESSDA follows.

We, at SoDaNet, continue through CESSDA, the journey within the European research ecosystem by acquiring better means to do the job we already do. The means provided include the following: information flow regarding data, easy exchange and expertise on mainstream data issues, such as trust and training, and networking. Last but not least, participation in projects provides us with knowledge, visibility and resources. Thus, we are looking forward to a future based data within CESSDA ERIC.”

- Dimitra Kondyli
Researcher, SoDaNet

of the abovementioned ERICs also started in 2016, with the aim of increasing visibility and impact with regard to decision makers and thus positively contribute to the sustainability of these ERICs and a possible widening of their activities. Closer cooperation is also encouraged for the management of daily activities and for tackling common issues and challenges for the social science and humanities ERICs. Joint efforts in awareness raising, especially in potential member countries were considered, as well as a combined top-down and bottom-up approach (i.e. joint conferences in collaboration with ministries, as well as support to potential Service Providers identified in non-member countries).

CESSDA has been on the ESFRI (European Strategic Forum for Research Infrastructures) roadmap from its first strategic document for the construction and development of the next generation of pan-European research infrastructures. In 2016, the commitment made by Member States and the European Commission in the Innovation Union flagship initiative to have implemented 60% of these ESFRI projects by the end of 2015 was fulfilled. 29 ESFRI Landmarks reached the implementation phase and these serve as hubs of scientific excellence. The [ESFRI Roadmap 2016](#) presented 21 ESFRI Projects, and CESSDA was among five landmarks in the social sciences and humanities.

In 2016, CESSDA was an official sponsor of the 3rd International European Social Survey (ESS) conference: “Understanding key challenges for European societies in the 21st century”, which took place in Switzerland on 13-15 July 2016 at the University of Lausanne. CESSDA was successfully represented in another ESS event: “International ESS Conference-Romania 2016”, which took place on 20-21 October 2016 in Bucharest, Romania.

ERIC Process

The process of transformation from CESSDA AS to CESSDA ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium) started in early 2015 with Step 1 of the application submitted in April 2015. The future structure of the ERIC with a Director and a General Assembly as the governing bodies was decided by the CESSDA General Assembly in mid-2015. Updated application materials (CESSDA ERIC Statutes, Technical and Scientific Description of CESSDA with annexes) were submitted to the European Commission on 1 December 2016 during Step 2 of the application. A majority of the current CESSDA members became the founding members of CESSDA ERIC. The formal decision and launch of CESSDA ERIC is expected mid-2017.

Upcoming Initiatives & Priorities for 2017

Work carried out in 2016 as part of the Work Plan 2016 has to be followed up and upgraded in 2017. Most of the projects funded in 2016 will be carried over to 2017, and 2017 Work Plan projects were approved by the General Assembly in November 2016. The Technical Framework project will continue its third phase of development. CESSDA Product and Service Catalogue phase 2 is scheduled to start in early 2017, along with several new tasks designed for 2017. Cooperation with Eurostat is an important part of future planned activities along with further developments with all current and newly submitted EU funded projects and proposals. CESSDA is also preparing for the new phase in its development and life-cycle with the formal establishment of CESSDA ERIC. Further growth of CESSDA Main Office is also planned in 2017.

[The Work Plan 2017](#) was adopted by the CESSDA General Assembly in November 2016 and will start in January 2017. This is the first Work Plan that is following the regular cycle procedure of proposing, developing and adopting work plan tasks. It consists of the following tasks:

Looking ahead

Work Plan 2017

- » Controlled Vocabularies (CV) Manager
- » CESSDA Expert Seminar 2017
- » CESSDA Product and Service Catalogue phase 2
- » CESSDA Metadata Management phase 2
- » CESSDA Technical Framework phase 3
- » CESSDA PID Policy
- » Data Discovery Workshops
- » Collaborative data management module for comparative social science researchers
- » Euro Question Bank phase 3
- » Trust 2017 activities

Future Membership

CESSDA is constantly trying to strengthen its current membership, and at the same time widen it to include new member countries and appointed Service Providers, thus expanding its pan-European coverage in providing access to social science data to the research community.

Current activities in that area are predominantly carried out in the framework of the CESSDA SaW project; on the one hand trying to establish general standards in research data management among current Service Providers (strengthening), and on the other, providing clear criteria for joining CESSDA for future member countries and their data archives (widening).

In 2016, as a direct result of widening efforts in the CESSDA SaW project, Hungary officially decided to join CESSDA and signed up as one of the founding members of CESSDA ERIC. Portugal is the next country in line from the extended CESSDA SaW network expected to join CESSDA in 2017. In parallel to that process, CESSDA continued extensive communication with Serbia and Ireland as possible new member countries, and renewed contacts with Italy, Romania and Spain.

Directors' Report for 2016

Business Enterprise Organisation Number: 912 125 912

CESSDA Board of Directors

Bergen, 1 June 2017

Date: 1 June 2017

Version: 1

Status: Final

Distribution: Open

The Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) was fully established in June 2013 as a permanent pan-European distributed research infrastructure that aims to provide large scale, integrated and sustainable data services to the social sciences. The main objective of CESSDA is to provide seamless access to data across data archives, national borders, languages and research areas and to increase the impact of the activities that are happening at a national level. CESSDA AS (Main Office) is a Norwegian limited liability company solely owned by the Norwegian Ministry of Education and Research, and functions as the legal vehicle and the coordination hub for the consortium. It is located in Bergen, Norway.

Activities

As foreseen in its statutes, mission of CESSDA is to provide a full scale sustainable research infrastructure that enables the research community to conduct high-quality research which in turn leads to effective solutions to the major challenges facing society today. The intention since its launch has been to progress rapidly to the European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) status. On the European level, CESSDA plays an important role in several major EC funded projects thus setting the standards in data management and access in Social Sciences and Humanities.

Funding

CESSDA is a consortium consisting of 15 European member countries and one observer country. According to the CESSDA Statutes the funding scheme shall be based on each country's GDP. Germany and Norway are paying disproportional annual amounts of respectively 750,000 and 800,000 Euros. The annual member fee contribution in 2014 was 1.9 million Euros, based on 13 member countries. In 2015, Greece and Belgium joined CESSDA and annual fee increased accordingly reaching 1.933 million Euros. This amount stayed the same in 2016.

Due to limited staff resources, some of the Work Plan 2016 tasks' duration was extended to the first quarter of 2017, with accompanying budgets carried over to 2017.

The Working Environment and the Natural Environment

The Main Office of CESSDA, at Parkveien 20, 5007 Bergen, had 5 employees in 2016.

CESSDA's employees work in an office environment with computers as their most used working tool. CESSDA employees are also required, on occasions, to travel abroad to perform their duties.

The amount of days of short-term sickness absence is low, zero days in 2016. Long-term sickness absence was not registered in 2016. No injuries or accidents were registered. CESSDA's activities have not polluted the natural environment.

Staff by Age and Gender

The gender distribution is three women and two men. There is a higher proportion of female employees (60%). CESSDA emphasises diversity and encourages qualified candidates to apply for jobs with us, regardless of age and cultural or ethnic background.

Annual Accounts

The financial performance for 2016 is positive. CESSDA is financially sound, and the company's prospects are good. The Board confirms that the requirements of the ongoing concern assumption are met. Annual net profit for 2016 was 0 NOK. Pursuant to the company's Statutes, no dividend is distributed.

Board of Directors and Director

Bjørn Henrichsen - Chair

Matthew Woollard - Vice-Chair

Dana Hamplova

Hans Jørgen Marker

Alexia Katsanidou

Roxane Silberman

Ron Dekker - Director

Financial Statement

CESSDA AS (registry no. 912 125 912)

Profit & Loss Statement 2016

Operating income and expenses (NOK)	NOTE	2016	2015
Other operating income	6	18 900 391	9 152 196
Operating Income		18 900 391	9 152 196
Payroll expenses	1	4 047 047	3 274 722
Depreciation and amortisation expense	4	68 700	65 400
Other operating expenses	1	13 894 326	7 669 009
Operating expenses		18 010 073	11 009 131
Operating profit		890 318	- 1 856 935
Financial income and expenses (NOK)	NOTE	2016	2015
Other interest income		28 151	15 108
Other financial income		92 579	2 474 644
Other interest expenses		0	2 178
Other financial expenses		1 011 048	630 639
Net financial income and expenses		- 890 318	1 856 935
Annual net profit		0	0

Balance Sheet

CESSDA AS (registry no. 912 125 912)

Balance Sheet 2016

Assets	NOTE	2016	2015
Fixed assets			
Tangible fixed assets			
Equipment and other movables	4	257 501	155 600
Total tangible fixed assets		257 501	155 600
Total fixed assets		257 501	155 600
Current assets			
Debtors			
Accounts receivable		592 826	185 789
Other receivables		890 318	204 099
Total debtors	5	600 877	389 888
Cash and bank deposits			
Cash and bank deposits	7	27 132 318	28 673 556
Total current assets		27 733 195	29 063 445
Total assets		27 990 696	29 219 045

Balance Sheet

CESSDA AS (registry no. 912 125 912)

Balance Sheet 2016

Equity and liabilities	NOTE	2016	2015
Equity			
Restricted equity			
Share capital (10 shares at NOK 5 000)	2, 3	50 000	50 000
Total restricted equity		50 000	50 000
Total equity	3	50 000	50 000
Liabilities			
Current liabilities			
Trade creditors		284 443	141 418
Deduction of tax and other public liabilities		266 458	150 360
Other short-term liabilities	6	6 591 837	4 624 032
Deferred income	6	20 797 958	24 253 235
Total short-term liabilities	5	27 940 696	29 169 045
Total liabilities		27 940 696	29 169 045
Total equity and liabilities		27 990 696	29 219 045

Notes to the Financial Statements

Accounting Principles

The accounts have been prepared in accordance with the Norwegian Accounting Act and good accounting practice in Norway. The accounting principles are described below.

Operating Income and Expenses

Dividends from investments in stocks and shares are recognized in the year in which they are received. Gains and losses are recognized in the year of realization, except when recognition in an earlier period is in accordance with good accounting practice.

Expenses are recognized in accordance with the matching principle. This means that expenses are recognized in the same period as the related income.

Classification of Assets and Liabilities

Assets meant for long-term ownership or use are classified as fixed assets. Other assets are classified as current assets. Outstanding receivables to be repaid within one year are classified as current assets. The classification of liabilities is based on analogous criteria.

Fixed assets are valued at acquisition cost. Fixed assets which have a limited economic life shall be depreciated in accordance with a reasonable depreciation schedule. Fixed assets shall be written down to their fair value when a decline in value is not expected to be temporary. The write down shall be reversed when the basis for the write down is no longer present.

Current assets are valued at the lower of acquisition cost and fair value. Liabilities are appraised at the nominal value on the acquisition date.

Currency

Assets in foreign currency are translated at the exchange rate on the date of the end of the fiscal year.

Taxes

Since the business is a not for profit organization it is not liable for corporation tax in accordance with Tax Law § 2-32.

Notes to the Financial Statements

Pension

The company has established a defined benefit pension scheme. The pension premium is classified as payroll expenses.

Notes

Note 1 – Payroll Expenses, Numbers of Employees, Loans to Employees etc

Payroll expenses consist of:

(All amounts in NOK)	2016	2015
Wages and holiday allowance	2 980 164	2 362 492
Payroll tax	497 232	404 182
Pension premium	296 302	239 726
Other benefits	273 349	26 8 321
Sum	4 047 047	3 274 722
Average number of full time equivalent	4,5	3

Total remuneration to the director was NOK 885 386.

In 2016 the Board of Directors received NOK 205 500 in fees.

The company is obliged to have a pension scheme according to the Norwegian Law of compulsory occupational pension scheme and have established a defined benefit pension scheme which satisfies the requirements. Employees have a pension scheme in Statens pensjonskasse (SPK).

Amounts paid to the company's auditor were NOK 28 800 for audit and NOK 17 400 for other services (amounts excl. VAT).

Notes to the Financial Statements

Note 2 – Ownership Structure

The company's share capital is NOK 50 000. The share capital comprises of 10 shares with a nominal value of NOK 5 000. The shares have equal voting rights.

On the 31 December the company had the following shareholders:

	No. shares	Stake
Kunnskapsdepartementet (Ministry of Education and Research)	50	100%

Note 3 – Changes in Equity

Shareholders' equity 01.01	50 000
Annual net profit	0
Shareholders' equity 31.12	50 000

Note 4 – Tangible Fixed Assets

(All amounts in NOK)

Fixtures, fittings and equipment

Acquisition cost 01.01	266 276
Purchase in accounting year	170 601
Acquisition cost 31.12	436 877
Accumulated depreciation	179 376
Book value 31.12	257 501
Annual depreciation	68 700
Expected economic life	3-5 years

Notes to the Financial Statements

Note 5 – Maturity of Receivables and Payables

Liabilities that fall due more than five years after the end of the accounting year are 0.

Receivables that fall due more than one year after the end of the accounting year are 0.

Note 6 – Breakdown of Income

Income in the year was derived from the following sources:

(All amounts in NOK)	2016	2015
Funding from Norwegian Research Council	7 452 160	7 410 640
Other grant income	10 263 126	11 635 672
Sum grant funding	17 715 286	19 046 312
Grants transferred from 2015 to 2016	0	-9 894 116
Transferred to operating income	11 185 105	0
Sum other operating income	18 900 391	9 152 196

Available as future operating budget:

(All amounts in NOK)	Deferred income
Deferred income pr. 01.01	14 359 119
Grant income	19 046 312
Operating expenses	- 11 009 131
Net financial income and expenses	1 846 935
Deferred income until 31.12	24 253 235

Note 7 – Fixed Assets

In the cash and bank deposits record are fixed tax deduction funds included with NOK 200 000 as of 31.12.2016.

Members of the General Assembly

Matthias Reiter-Pázmándy (until June) & Thomas Kreuzer & Ursula Brustmann (after June) - Austria
Laurence Lenoir & Aziz Naji - Belgium
Petr Ventluka & Jindrich Krejci - Czech Republic
Anne Sofie Fink & Troels Rasmussen - Denmark
Petteri Kauppinen & Sami Borg - Finland
Gilles Ohanessian & Bertrand Jouve - France
Monika van Ooyen & Christof Wolf - Germany
Nicolas Demertzis & Dimitra Kondyli - Greece
Algis Krupavicius - Lithuania
Peter Doorn & Joris Voskuilen - Netherlands
Hege Torp & Kari Balke Øiseth - Norway
Miloslav Bahna & Robert Klobucky - Slovakia
Albin Kralj - Slovenia
Susanna Bylin & Staffan Marklund - Sweden
Peter Farago & Brian Kleiner - Switzerland
Paul Meller (until September) & Hilary Beedham (until August) - United Kingdom

Members of the Board of Directors

Bjorn Henrichsen - Chair
Matthew Woollard - Vice Chair

Dana Hamplova
Alexia Katsanidou (from April)
Hans Jørgen Marker
Roxane Silberman
Anne Westendorp (until October)

Members of the Scientific Advisory Board

Myron Gutmann - Chair
Bernt Aardal
Denise Lievesley
Nancy Pedersen
Simon Hodson
Tomaz Smrekar

Members of the Service Providers' Forum

Matthias Reiter-Pázmándy (until June) & Hajo Boomgarden & Lars Kaszmirek (after June) - Austria
Jindrich Krejci & Yana Leontiyeva - CSDA, Czech Republic
Anne Sofie Fink - DDA, Denmark
Sami Borg & Helena Laaksonen - FSD, Finland
Roxane Silberman - CNRS, France
Alexia Katsanidou - GESIS, Germany
Dimitra Kondyli - So.Da.Net, Greece
Algis Krupavicius - LiDA, Lithuania
Marnix van Berchum (until September) & Heiko Tjalsma (from September) - DANS, Netherlands
Vigdis Kvalheim - NSD, Norway
Miloslav Bahna - SASD, Slovakia (observer)
Janez Stebe - ADP, Slovenia
Iris Alfredsson & Hans Jørgen Marker - SND, Sweden
Brian Kleiner - FORS, Switzerland
Hilary Beedham (until August) & David Hall (after August) - UKDA, United Kingdom

Organisation

Organisational Map (on 31.12.2016)

The Main Office (MO) of CESSDA is located at Parkveien 20, in Bergen, Norway.

In 2016 there were five employees in the Main Office:

Acting Administrative Director - Ivana Ilijašić Veršić

Administrative Secretary - Nina Bakanova

Senior Communication Officer - Eleanor Smith

Chief Technical Officer - Hossein Abroshan

Senior Project Manager - Jean-Baptiste Milon

CESSDA AS

Parkveien 20

5007 Bergen

Norway

+47 55 58 36 48

cessda@cessda.eu

@CESSDA_Data

www.cessda.eu